

Cu-**CHA** zeolite-based catalysts for the selective catalytic reduction of NO_x in exhaust diesel gas: addressing the issue of **Sulfur Stability**

Deliverable 7.3 (D42)

CHASS Data Management Plan

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The CHASS project

CHASS is an H2020-MSCA ITN-EID project which aims to educate four PhD students. The project targets deactivation of SCR catalysts for NO_x removal from diesel exhaust gases, with special focus on poisoning by SO₂ and exposures to high temperatures. The aim is to build models based on a fundamental chemical understanding of the catalysts, which can be applied in the development of future exhaust systems.

See <http://chass-itn-project.eu> for more information.

Project partners

(Coordinator, academic, University of Torino)

(Academic, Chalmers University of Technology in Gothenburg)

(Industrial, Umicore Denmark ApS and Umicore AG & Co KG)

About this document

This reports deliverable D7.3 (D42) of the CHASS MSCA-ITN project. It was prepared by:

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Document History

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Executive Summary

The data management plan (DMP) gives an overview over the data generated in the project, how this data will be handled and stored and made publicly available. The DMP is a working document and will be updated during the lifetime of the project when necessary. As a minimum, the DPM will be updated in the context of the periodic evaluation/assessment of the project, and in time for the final review at the latest.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
Table of Contents	4
1. Data summary	5
1.1. Purpose of data collection and generation, and relation to project objectives	5
1.2. Data formats and types, and origin	5
1.3. Re-use of data	5
1.4. Data utility	5
2. FAIR Data	6
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	6
2.2. Making data openly accessible	6
2.3. Making data interoperable	7
2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	7
3. Allocation of resources	7
4. Data security	7
5. Ethical aspects	8
6. Other issues	8

1. Data summary

1.1. Purpose of data collection and generation, and relation to project objectives

The sole purpose of the data collection and generation is to achieve the project goals, as described in the project plan. Specifically, this encompasses catalyst characterization and testing, DFT calculations and microkinetic modeling. Data generation, collection and analysis are an essential part of the research activity of the CHASS consortium. Data are generated as a result of the experimental and modelling activity. Once collected they are validated and subsequently interpreted to build new knowledge and models based on a fundamental chemical understanding of the studied catalyst activity and stability, which is the primary objective of the project.

1.2 Data formats and types, and origin

The research proposed is not of such nature that very large data amounts, suitable for storage in databases, will be produced. The data generated in the project will be results of catalytic tests and kinetic analysis, spectra, structures and related energetic values. The most widely used CSV, MS Excel, DAT, ASCII format will be used for numerical data, which are typically placed in spreadsheets, where records are plotted against variables or measurements. Plain text (.txt), MS word, Rich Text Format and PDF files will be also produced. Proprietary format data are usually converted into standard CSV or xlsx format. Graphs resulting from the experiments could be transformed into open file formats for images (JPEG).

Source	Format	Size	Origin
Characterization	csv, xlsx, dat, txt, pdf, jpeg	<10GB	experimental measurements
Catalytic testing	csv, xlsx, dat, txt, pdf, opj	<10GB	experimental measurements
DFT calculations	csv, xlsx, dat, txt, pdf,	TBD	VASP https://www.vasp.at/
Kinetic modeling	csv, xlsx, dat, txt, pdf	TBD	Simulation (MATLAB)

1.3 Re-use of data

Physical samples, experimental methods, unpublished experimental data, models, structures and energetic profiles from partners can be used as a starting point to address the project goals. Reuse is allowed based on bi- or multi-lateral IP agreements.

1.4 Data utility

The primary users of the data will be the project partners and the researchers within. In addition, the data produced will be of use to the research community in the field of heterogeneous catalysis and of any enterprise operating in the field of automotive catalysts.

2. FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data that is made available outside of the project will be accompanied by relevant metadata. CHASS metadata comply with the “DataCite Metadata Schema”’s minimum requirements in their V4.3 Version (<https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.3/>), which are in line with the metadata requested by [Zenodo](#).

Table 1: DataCite Mandatory Properties

<i>ID</i>	<i>Property</i>	<i>Obligation</i>
1	Identifier (with mandatory type sub-property)	M
2	Creator (with optional given name, family name, name identifier and affiliation sub-properties)	M
3	Title (with optional type sub-properties)	M
4	Publisher	M
5	PublicationYear	M
10	ResourceType (with mandatory general type description sub-property)	M

Table 1 source: DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2019). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data. Version 4.3. DataCite e.V. <https://doi.org/10.14454/7xq3-zf69>

All public data will be assigned a searchable digital object identifier (DOI) number, assigned by the journals for papers and by [Zenodo](#) for paper-related datasets. The naming of the paper-related datasets will be decided with the aim to make them findable and understandable to people working in the field (e.g. DFT calculated structures, kinetic calculations, IR spectra, etc). Each separate file will follow the conventional name proposed by partner having created it.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

Data connected to publications will be made openly available together with the publication. Data and procedures will be made available and documented via the use of extended supplementary material attached to regular research articles to allow straightforward reproduction by others. Data connected to trade secrets will not be made public.

Public data will be made available as supplementary material to publications and/or by being deposited in a repository. In both case the data will have a digital object identifier (DOI).

Each partner can choose a repository for open access data. Both Universities have repository services available to ensure open access after a certain embargo period, which are mandatory to use. Moreover, Chalmers has introduced an Open Access Policy, in accordance with the Berlin Declaration on Open Access, to which the Association of Swedish Higher Education is a signatory. A CHAS community site will be created at [Zenodo](#) to be used as a repository for publications, metadata and public deliverable of CHASS.

A link to research open data and publications in general will be provided on the project website (<https://www.chass-itn-project.eu>). No special tools will be needed to access the data.

2.3 Making data interoperable

The standard scientific language is used, which is common ground for all scientists and practitioners in the field. Catalyst testing and kinetic data will use widely acceptable terminologies such as flow rates, conversions, selectivity and yields. Characterization data will use widely accepted terminologies in the related field.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Whether data will be made available for re-use, will be a case-to-case decision. Based on the enterprises necessity to guarantee industrial secrets and possibilities of future commercial exploitation. This procedure of pre-approval before publication is set in the Consortium Agreement, Section 8.4.2.

Data for re-use will be licenced using creative commons licencing under consideration of the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle. The type of licence is dependent on IPR and planned exploitation. If needed, the data made will be made available for re-use after an embargo period.

3. Allocation of resources

Data management, including secure storage, is the responsibility of the project partners handling the data in question. Some data will be stored in the University of Torino (UNITO) secure server, some data (presentations, literature, meeting minutes etc) will be shared among the project partners in a share point in Microsoft Teams, with restricted access. This system has been used by some of the partners for different research projects. Public data will be stored in Zenodo. Storing data in UNITO secure server is free of cost for UNITO staff, the same holds for the share point created in Microsoft Teams for the staff working on CHASS. Zenodo will host less than 1 GigaByte of CHASS data, meaning that data stored in Zenodo up to 2032 will be free of cost. Hence, there will be no costs associated to data storage.

No costs will be associated to 'green open access' self-archiving in the two Universities repositories (<https://iris.unito.it/>; <https://research.chalmers.se/en/>). This includes the final peer-reviewed manuscripts and the editorial pdf, which will be available after an embargo period. Self-archiving in these repositories is compulsory for both Universities. In some cases the partners could decide to publish in 'gold open access'. The related publication costs will be covered by Institutional costs of the partners if deemed suitable. Moreover, Chalmers has a deal with different editors to publish open access and faculty money is available to support open access publishing with other publishers (<https://www.lib.chalmers.se/en/publish-and-analyse/open-access/publish-oa-paid-for-by-the-library/>). UNITO has signed an ACS Read + Publish agreement as a member of the CRUI – Conferenza dei Rettori consortium. This implies that UNITO staff can have access at some vouchers for publication in ACS 'gold open access' journals. More information on Chalmers OA policy: <https://www.lib.chalmers.se/en/publish-and-analyse/open-access/introduction-to-open-access-oa/>

4. Data security

Every partner has responsibility for data recovery and secure data storage for the data they generate as well as for the data they receive from other project partners. Partners will follow national and international rules, especially in respect to personal data (GDPR regulations).

Regular backup on local hardware of all project data is recommended to all staff members, so that data recovery is always possible.

Zenodo respects the highest standards for data security, as shown at the link <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>.

Transfer of sensitive data: Sensitive data will be transferred using WeTransfer. It is GDPR compliant (<https://wetransfer.zendesk.com/hc/enus/articles/210092453-How-secure-is-your-platform->) and, in CHASS's case, would store our files in the EU (<https://wetransfer.zendesk.com/hc/enus/articles/210092443-Where-do-you-store-my-files->).

5. Ethical aspects

No sensitive data related to personal data will be generated in the project.

6. Other issues